

Eco-Friendly Synthesis of Silver Oxide Nanoparticles Using *Ipomea asarifolia* Leaf Extract and Evaluation of Their Antimicrobial Properties

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Abstract

This study focuses on the green synthesis and characterization of silver oxide nanoparticles (Ag₂O NPs) using *Ipomea asarifolia* leaf extract as both a reducing and stabilizing agent, with emphasis on their antimicrobial properties. The extract successfully facilitated the reduction of silver ions (Ag⁺) into nanoparticles evidenced by a color change to reddish-brown. The synthesized nanoparticles were analyzed using UV-Vis spectroscopy, FTIR, TEM, XRD, SEM, and EDX. UV-Vis results showed peak absorption at around 430 nm. TEM images revealed primarily spherical particles with some agglomeration, averaging 14.80 nm in size. XRD confirmed the crystalline nature of Ag₂O with peaks at 37.00°, 45.00°, 55.00°, and 65.70°. SEM further supported the spherical morphology, and EDX indicated a strong presence of elemental silver. FTIR analysis confirmed metal-oxygen and hydroxyl group vibrations at 550 cm⁻¹ and 790 cm⁻¹, suggesting that phytochemicals like flavonoids and phenols in the extract played roles in reduction and stabilization. Antimicrobial testing showed that the synthesized Ag₂O NPs were effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, with stronger inhibition observed against Gram-negative strains. A clear dose-dependent response was observed across tested bacterial pathogens.

Keywords: *Nanoparticles, Ipomea asarifolia, phytochemicals, Antimicrobial.*

Introduction

The rise of antibiotic-resistant pathogens poses a significant threat to global health, largely due to the misuse of conventional antibiotics. This has led to an urgent demand for alternative antimicrobial agents, especially those derived from natural, eco-friendly, and non-toxic sources. Among these, silver-based nanoparticles have attracted considerable attention for their unique physicochemical properties and broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity (Ibraheem *et al.*, 2016; Hamed *et al.*, 2017). Silver oxide nanoparticles (Ag₂O NPs) are particularly valuable due to their potential applications in antimicrobial treatments and catalysis (Manikandan *et al.*, 2017; Alsamhary, 2020). Conventional physical and chemical

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synthesis methods, such as sol-gel, microwave, and electrochemical approaches, often involve toxic chemicals, high energy consumption, and expensive equipment. These drawbacks have steered research toward greener alternatives (Bokov *et al.*, 2021; Chupradit *et al.*, 2022; Akbarizadeh *et al.*, 2022). Biological synthesis—especially plant-mediated approaches—offers a sustainable and safer route to nanoparticle production (Ameen *et al.*, 2021; Xie *et al.*, 2022). Plant extracts are rich in natural compounds like flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, alkaloids, and proteins, which serve as natural reducing and capping agents (Mortezaghali *et al.*, 2022; Alijani *et al.*, 2022). This method not only reduces environmental impact but also simplifies the synthesis process, eliminating the need for high pressure, temperature, or hazardous chemicals (Ngafwan *et al.*, 2021; Ali *et al.*, 2022). Numerous plant species have been used to synthesize Ag₂O NPs, including *Zephyranthes rosea* (Maheshwaran *et al.*, 2020), *Centella asiatica* (Rashmi *et al.*, 2020), *Citrus limon* (Alkhulaifi *et al.* 2020) and *Cleome gynandra* (Mani *et al.*, 2021). However, the use of *Ipomea asarifolia* in nanoparticle synthesis remains underexplored. This plant contains various bioactive compounds capable of reducing and stabilizing metal ions, making it a cost-effective and eco-friendly option (Zayed *et al.*, 2022). The novelty of this study lies in utilizing *Ipomea asarifolia* leaf extract for the green synthesis of silver oxide nanoparticles. The synthesized NPs were comprehensively characterized, and their antimicrobial effectiveness was evaluated, highlighting their potential applications in combating bacterial infections and promoting environmental sustainability.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals

Silver nitrate (AgNO₃) and Sodium hydroxide pellets (NaOH) used in this study were secured from Sigma-Aldrich Company.

Collection and Identification of Plant Sample

Fresh *Ipomea asarifolia* leaves were collected from the grounds of the College of Nursing and Midwifery Sciences, located in Tambuwal, Tambuwal Local Government Area, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The plant was taxonomically identified at the Herbarium Unit of the Department of Biological Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, where a specimen was prepared and deposited, and a voucher number was obtained for reference.

Preparation and Extraction of Plant Material

Fresh *Ipomea asarifolia* leaves were cleaned, air-dried for seven days, then oven-dried at 60°C to remove moisture. The dried leaves were ground into powder, and 10 g of this powder was boiled with 100 ml of distilled water to prepare the plant extract. After cooling and filtration using Muslim cloth followed by Whatman No.1 filter paper, the extract was used for the green synthesis of silver (AgNPs).

Synthesis of the Silver Nanoparticle (AgNPs)

To synthesize Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), 10 mL of *Ipomea asarifolia* leaf extract was mixed with 100 mL of 1 mM silver nitrate (AgNO₃) solution and stirred at room temperature for 90 minutes. The mixture was kept in a dark chamber to prevent photoactivation. A color change from bright yellow to reddish-brown indicated nanoparticle formation. The AgNPs were separated by centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes, washed 3–4 times with deionized water and ethanol, then dried at 130°C and stored in an airtight container for future use (Fuad *et al.*, 2023).

Characterization of the Nanoparticles

The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized using a variety of analytical techniques to determine their structural, morphological, and functional properties. UV–visible spectroscopy was conducted using a Shimadzu 1601 spectrophotometer, scanning within the 300–800 nm wavelength range to confirm nanoparticle formation. The crystalline structure of the nanoparticles was analyzed using an X-ray diffractometer (Shimadzu XRD-6000) with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$). Surface morphology and elemental composition were investigated using a scanning electron microscope (JOEL JSM 7600F) equipped with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Functional groups present in both the *Ipomoea asarifolia* leaf extract and the synthesized nanoparticles were identified using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), performed with a Thermo 6700 spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) across the spectral range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} . Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to assess the particle size and morphology. TEM micrographs were captured using a JEM-1400 (JEOL Ltd., Japan) operating at an accelerating voltage of 100 kV (Manal *et al.*, 2020).

Antibacterial Activity

The antimicrobial activity of the synthesized nanoparticles was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method against clinical strains of *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae*. Standardized bacterial suspensions (OD 0.1) were spread on nutrient agar plates, and 7 mm wells were filled with various concentrations of nanoparticle suspensions (0.025–0.2 mg/mL). After allowing diffusion, plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Zones of inhibition were measured to assess antibacterial efficacy, with Ciprofloxacin used as a positive control (Shamaila *et al.*, 2016).

Results and Discussion

UV–Visible spectrophotometry Analysis

Figure 1. Shows the UV–Visible Absorption Spectrum of (AgNPs) Synthesized Using *I. AE*. A Broad Absorption Peak was Observed around 430 nm, Indicating the Formation of AgNPs

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis

Figure 2. XRD Pattern of Fe NPs-IA

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Analysis

Figure 3. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Result Analysis of AgNPs Synthesized by *I asarifolia* Extract

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis

Figure 4. SEM Images of Green Synthesized Ag NPs

Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) Analysis

Figure 5. Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) Spectrum of the Synthesized AgNPs

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) Analysis

Figure 6. TEM Images of the Synthesized AgNPs

Figure 7. Antibacterial Activity of Silver Nanoparticles against Representative Microorganisms

Discussions

Synthesis and Mechanism of Nanoparticles

This study developed a cost-effective, eco-friendly method for synthesizing Ag_2O using *Ipomoea asarifolia* extract as a natural reducing, stabilizing, and capping agent. When the extract was mixed with AgNO_3 , a gradual color change to reddish-brown confirmed the formation of AgNPs, aligning with previous research findings (Fuad *et al.*, 2023; Jain *et al.*, 2021). The observed color change during nanoparticle synthesis is due to interactions between metal ions and phytochemicals particularly flavonoids and phenolics in *Ipomoea asarifolia* extract (Anchan *et al.*, 2019). These compounds, especially their hydroxyl and

carbonyl groups, donate electrons to reduce Ag^+ to $\text{Ag}^0/\text{Ag}_2\text{O}$ and Fe^{3+} to $\text{Fe}^0/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$. The reduced metal atoms then nucleate and grow into stable metal oxide nanoparticles. Additionally, these bioactive compounds act as capping agents, preventing nanoparticle aggregation and ensuring a stable, well-dispersed colloidal system (Elegbede *et al.*, 2019; Devi *et al.*, 2019). This green synthesis method yields stable and functional Ag_2O and Fe_2O_3 NPs with promising applications in medicine, water purification, and antimicrobial treatments. The biosynthesis is driven by phytochemicals in *Ipomoea asarifolia*, which mediate the reduction and stabilization of metal ions. The proposed electron donation from functional groups particularly hydroxyl group leading to nanoparticle formation, is illustrated below:

Ag-NPs UV-Visible Spectrophotometry Analysis

The formation of (AgNPs) was monitored through UV-Vis spectroscopy and visual color changes in the reaction mixture. Initially, the reaction mixture exhibited a greyish-white appearance, which transitioned to yellowish-brown, and eventually to a reddish-brown color, indicating the successful formation of AgNPs, resulting from the reduction of silver ion (Ag^+) to metallic silver (Ag^0) by bioactive compounds in the *Ipomoea asarifolia* extract. The color change is attributed to the excitation of surface plasmon resonance (SPR), a hallmark of NPs formation. The UV-Vis spectrum showed an SPR peak around 430 nm, confirming the nanocrystalline nature of Ag_2O NPs as shown in Figure 1. This SPR peak is characteristic of small-sized silver NPs and aligns with findings reported by Rokade *et al.*, (2016), Okafor *et al.*, (2013), and Manikandan *et al.*, (2017).

Ag-NPs X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis

The XRD pattern of AgNPs synthesized with *I. asarifolia* leaf extract showed prominent peaks at the angles of 37.00° , 45.00° , 55.00° , 65.70° corresponding to the planes of (220), (300), and (311), respectively, confirming the formation of Ag_2O NPs crystals (Fig. 3). Additional peaks observed at 9.7° , 24.50° , 27.00° , 28.5° were attributed to organic compounds from the extract, which contribute to the reduction and stabilization of the nanoparticles (Roopan *et al.*, 2013). The obtained results are consistent with previous results reported by other researchers (Kumar, Palanichamy & Roopan, 2014; Redjili *et al.*, 2024).

AgNPs Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Analysis

FT-IR analysis was used to identify functional groups in *I. asarifolia* extract involved in the synthesis and stabilization of AgNPs. The spectrum before reacting with AgNO_3 showed key peaks at 3446.3, 2930.0, 1796.12, and 874.15 cm^{-1} , corresponding to O-H, N-H, C-H, and C=O groups. The prominent O-H peak indicated a high content of phenolic compounds, suggesting their key role as reducing agents in NPs formation (Sharath *et al.*, 2023). Following the reaction with AgNO_3 , noticeable shifts in peak positions were observed from 3446.3 to 3445.00 cm^{-1} , 2930.00 to 2929.00 cm^{-1} , 1796.12 to 1612.00 cm^{-1} , and 874.15 to 790.42 cm^{-1} —along with the appearance of a new peak at 642.4 cm^{-1} , suggesting the active involvement of hydroxyl, carboxyl, groups from the *I. asarifolia* extract in the reduction and stabilization of AgNPs (Bankar *et al.*, 2010). Ag_2O NPs displayed a strong absorption band around 550 cm^{-1} , indicating Ag-O stretching (Kadam *et al.*, 2016), 790 cm^{-1} associated with Ag-O bending. These characteristic peaks confirm the successful formation of Ag_2O NPs (Fayyadh and Jadua Alzubaidy, 2021).

AgNPs Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis

Figure 7 displays the SEM images of the green-synthesized Ag_2O NPs, highlighting valuable information on their morphology, size, and aggregation behavior. SEM images of the green-synthesized Ag_2O nanoparticles revealed predominantly spherical particles averaging around 50 nm in size.

Noticeable aggregation was observed, likely due to capping by *Ipomoea asarifolia* extract, which reduced interparticle spacing. This confirmed the extract dual role as both a stabilizing and capping agent, limiting particle growth and supporting the formation of uniform, small-sized NPs (Lateef *et al.*, 2018). These findings are consistent with previous studies by (Sharath *et al.*, 2023; Manikandan *et al.*, 2017).

AgNPs Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) Analysis

The EDX spectrum (Fig. 9) confirmed the elemental composition of silver NPs synthesized using *I. asarifolia*. A strong peak at 1.5 keV confirmed the presence of silver, consistent with previous studies (Kazeem *et al.*, 2024). Additional peaks at 0.14, 0.46, and 0.77 keV represent oxygen, carbon, and nitrogen, originating from phytochemicals in the plant extract. The dominant signal at 1.5 keV aligns with previous reports indicating silver presence typically within the 1.5–5.0 keV range (Aina *et al.*, 2020; Lateef *et al.*, 2018). Quantitative analysis showed a high silver content (60.96%), along with oxygen (25.67%), carbon (10.32%), and nitrogen (8.02%), emphasizing the extract's role in reducing and stabilizing the nanoparticles during synthesis.

AgNPs Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) Analysis

TEM analysis (Fig. 11) revealed that the synthesized Ag₂O nanoparticles were predominantly spherical, with sizes ranging from 4.42 nm to 30.34 nm and an average size of approximately 14.80 nm. The uniform morphology and nanoscale distribution indicate effective stabilization by bioactive compounds in *Ipomoea asarifolia* extract. These results align with the spherical structure previously observed in SEM images.

Determination of Antibacterial Activity of the Green Synthesized AgNPs

The antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles synthesized using *I. asarifolia* leaf extract was evaluated against two Gram-positive and two Gram-negative bacteria (Fig. 13). At the highest concentration (0.2 mg/mL), AgNPs showed strong inhibition against *K. pneumoniae* (25 ± 0.1 mm), *E. coli* (20 ± 0.3 mm), and *B. subtilis* (20 ± 0.2 mm), while *S. aureus* showed no inhibition. Lower concentrations produced smaller inhibition zones indicating the antibacterial effect was concentration-dependent, and the extract alone was active only against *B. subtilis*. Overall, Gram-negative bacteria were more susceptible to AgNPs than Gram-positive strains, likely due to their thinner peptidoglycan layer, which allows better interaction with the nanoparticles. Gram-negative bacteria have a thinner peptidoglycan layer, facilitating more effective interaction between the NPs and the bacterial membrane (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2007).

Conclusion

This study successfully demonstrated the green synthesis of silver (Ag) nanoparticles using *Ipomoea asarifolia* leaf extract as a natural reducing and stabilizing agent. The method is simple, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable, presenting a viable alternative to traditional chemical synthesis. Characterization confirmed the formation of stable, nanoscale Ag₂O and Fe₂O₃ particles with desirable structural and morphological traits. The synthesized nanoparticles exhibited strong antibacterial activity, especially against drug-resistant pathogens, highlighting their potential as novel antimicrobial agents. The findings validate the presence of bioactive phytochemicals in *I. asarifolia* capable of mediating nanoparticle synthesis. However, further studies are recommended to assess the cytotoxicity and safety profiles of these nanoparticles for biomedical applications.

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